

LEGAL REGULATION OF E-COMMERCE RELATIONS UNDER THE LEGISLATION OF THE EUROPEAN UNION AND CENTRAL ASIAN STATES: COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this work is to consider the legal regulation of e-commerce relations and conduct a comparative legal analysis of the legislation of the EU and Central Asia. This work is aimed to study the weaknesses and strengths of each system, develop special theoretical and practical proposals to improve the quality of regulatory legal acts. In general, the study is aimed at providing the necessary information and recommendations for improving the field of electronic commercial law.

The rapid development of e-commerce during the pandemic has become a pronounced trend. Therefore, with such dynamics, it is necessary to develop public relations at the proper level to ensure the protection of the rights and interests of online consumers and professional participants in e-commerce.

E-commerce is one of the most developing areas of application of the World Wide Web. Its technical basis is modern network technologies, but its essence lies in the use of a single Internet information space to increase the effectiveness of communication between participants in commercial transactions. From the point of view of importance for the largest number of people, the most important area of e-commerce should be recognized as e-commerce - the technology of promoting goods and services to the market using the Internet.

The rapid growth of e-commerce has shown the need to develop this institution not only from the market and technological aspects, but also in terms of regulatory support. Creating favorable conditions for entrepreneurs and consumers will facilitate the practice of digital consumption.

E-commerce is quite specific. The fact is that when selling goods, the seller may not meet with the buyer. That is, potential buyers can contact the company's server and place an order at any time and from anywhere in the world. In addition, goods such as books, magazines, and musical works are sometimes distributed in digital format. Finally, the goods can be delivered to the buyer in an unconventional way. For example, custom-made software products are usually sent to the customer by e-mail.

The main regulatory legal act that established the key concepts and rules for the functioning of e-commerce was the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On e-commerce".

An important aspect, in our opinion, was the positive dynamics in the legislator's understanding of the term e-commerce itself from the standpoint of civil law perception.

In its technologies, the objective process of globalization, integration and digitalization, which became the reason for the development of the new truth "Digital Economy" in Kazakhstan, which today is one of the most promising and fast-growing areas of business organization that have passed several key stages, served as the basis for the intensive development of modern trade, increasing its role in the global and national economy. At the same time, digitalization is understood as the fullest use of the available potential of digital technologies in all possible aspects of business management: processes, products, services, as well as ways of making managerial decisions. While in the traditional economy, trade is mainly rich in production potential and technological development, in the network economy, the development of e-commerce and increasing its competitiveness is largely determined by the development of e-commerce infrastructure.

The use of information technology in developed countries is characterized by widespread and high rates of implementation in all sectors of the economy. One of the most dynamically developing regions of developing economies is, of course, electronic commerce. Prerequisites for the formation and development of an electronic trading system in Kazakhstan: fundamental sciences and applied sciences, as well as the level of modern theoretical achievements of intellectual, creative teams of scientific industry competencies in the field of national, managerial and economic, development of information technologies, trade, electronic commerce and Internet business achieved in the country and the world¹.

Electronic commerce includes such transactions provided for by the Civil Code of Turkmenistan as purchase and sale, delivery, transportation, loan, banking, storage, insurance, assignment, trust management of property, competition and others, as well as the acquisition and exercise of other rights and obligations in the field of entrepreneurial activity.

According to Article 6 of the Model Law "On Electronic Commerce" all electronic transactions in an electronic commerce transaction must be executed in accordance with the requirements and procedure established by the agreement of the parties and the legislation of Turkmenistan. An agreement in electronic commerce is drawn up as a result of agreeing on the terms of the agreement and forming it through the exchange of electronic documents between the parties to an electronic transaction. An electronic contract is defined as a civil law contract carried out on the basis of the use of electronic information systems, telecommunication communication systems and electronic procedures.

V.A.Kopylov, for example, notes: "Since the Internet is primarily an information environment, the information sphere model is fully applicable for its research. And therefore, when researching this environment, it is advisable to rely on an information approach based primarily on the methods of legal informatics and legal cybernetics"².

As you know, a transaction in civil science is defined as an action of legal entities aimed at establishing, changing or terminating civil rights and obligations. In this form, the definition of a transaction is reflected in article 178 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Tajikistan:

¹ Idrys S.S., Almukhambetova B.Z., Shen B... The development of electronic trading system in Kazakhstan. Bulletin of "Turan" University. 2019;(1):227-232.

² Kopylov V.A. Information Law. - M.: Jurist, 2004. - p. 237.

“Transactions are recognized as actions of citizens and legal entities aimed at establishing, changing and terminating civil rights and obligations”.

From the above definition, it becomes clear that transactions, as a means of individual regulation of public relations, legally represent a set of regulatory requirements for a socially significant act of behavior of a legal entity. The permissive nature of civil law requires the legislator not only to indicate the essential features for the qualification of a transaction, but also to formulate regulatory requirements for characteristics of a transaction other than essential features as a legal phenomenon.

According to the law of the European Union, a consumer is an individual who, at the conclusion of a contract, acts in the interests of satisfying his personal, household needs that are not related to business activities. The consumer is recognized not only by the person who purchased the goods, but also by the person who only has the intention to do so. Therefore, it is possible to consider the specifics of consumer protection in the implementation of electronic relations in accordance with the law of the European Union at various stages of the development of consumer relations and its counterparties. Starting with the receipt of information, often preceding the conclusion of a contract, and ending with the transfer of goods to the consumer and the provision of guarantees³.

When developing and forming the Law “On E-Commerce”, it is necessary to consider the experience of other states that widely use e-commerce. The most important from the point of view of the issue under consideration are the legal documents developed by the European Union: Directive 97/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of May 20, 1997 “On consumer protection in the case of long-distance contracts”, Directive No. 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of the EU on certain legal aspects of information services in the domestic market, in particular, on e-commerce (E-Commerce Directive) (Luxembourg, 8 June 2000), as well as Directive 97/66/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union of December 15, 1997, concerning the use of personal data and the protection of privacy in the field of telecommunications. For certain reasons, e-commerce has developed much more passively in the European Union than it did in the United States. It can be said that the countries of the European Union turned out to be more distrustful of e-commerce, so it was more difficult for European Union entrepreneurs to obtain financial support for this field of activity⁴.

Also, e-commerce entrepreneurs faced difficulties, unlike in the United States, which contained certain organizational difficulties related to the fragmentation and lack of a uniform approach to the legislative regulation of e-commerce. It can be said that interactive information services, which were widely popular in the European Union, also influenced the growth of interest in the Internet. Also, one of the most significant obstacles to the widespread use of the Internet in the European Union was the cost of telephone services, which was calculated by per-minute billing. After a skeptical start, e-commerce has shown strong growth

³ Nekoteneva M. V. Chapter 19 // The law of the European Union. Special part : textbook for bachelors / S. Y. Kashkin ; ed. by S. Y. Kashkin. 4th ed., reprint. and additional M. : Yurait, 2019. Vol. 2. p. 472.

⁴ The Model Law on Electronic Commerce of the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (Adopted at the 29th session of the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law. Recommended by General Assembly resolution 51/162 of December 16, 1996).

https://www.un.org/ru/documents/decl_conv/conventions/commerce.shtml (accessed: 1.01.2021).

and reached its current level, e-commerce is now widely popular among business participants in both the United States and the European Union.

The legal field of e-commerce is very wide, which covers issues arising in the course of commercial relations, namely: purchase and sale, supply, product distribution agreements, factoring, leasing, trade representation or agency, consulting, engineering, investment contracts, banking services, insurance, operating and concession agreements, joint activities and other forms of industrial and business cooperation, including cargo transportation and passenger transportation by air, sea, and rail. As noted earlier, there is currently no Law on Electronic Commerce in the Republic of Kazakhstan and its adoption will make it possible to determine the legal status of suppliers, consumers, the procedure necessary to conclude a contract or cancel erroneous orders⁵.

The purpose of creating special rules is to provide legal guarantees to all participants in business activities in the field of e-commerce. Regulation of e-commerce is provided by the legal provisions provided for in the exchange of electronic documents. Ensuring trust in an electronic signature is a mandatory element of concluding contracts, as well as transferring ownership rights and binding rights when using electronic document management. The legal principle of e-commerce is that the parties who have concluded a contract do not have the right to question the validity and binding nature of the contract just because it is concluded in electronic form. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, such a principle is implemented through an agreement between the parties to the contract, in the case of its conclusion or implementation in electronic form.

In accordance with Articles 5 and 6 of the Consumer Rights Directive, all information must be provided in a clear and understandable form, and this requirement applies to the terms of the contract and to any other information relevant to the buyer. Directive 2000/31/EC establishes additional requirements for the information provided. Articles 5, 6 of this Directive contain, for example, requirements that commercial communication must be clearly defined as such; promotional offers — such as, for example, discounts, bonuses and gifts — must be clearly identifiable as such, and the conditions to be met in the promotional offer must be easily achievable and presented clearly and unambiguously; contests or games must be clearly identifiable as such, and the conditions of participation must be easily achievable and they are presented clearly and unambiguously.

In the case of registration of the contract via the Internet, additional guarantees are provided, in particular, the inclusion of predefined values is prohibited. The information provided at the time of conclusion of the contract and after that is regulated, in particular, in Articles 10, 11 of Directive 2000/31/EC. These include data: whether the concluded contract will be stored with the service provider and whether it will be available; technical means for detecting and correcting errors before placing an order; the requirement that the terms of the contract and the general provisions submitted to the recipient must be accessible to such an extent that he can store and reproduce them. In accordance with a special rule, in case of non-fulfillment of information obligations related to additional payments, the cost of expenses may be charged to the seller.

⁵ Mengliev Sh.M. The objective need to unify the norms of private international law. Civil legislation: Articles. Comments. Practice. Issue 29. Almaty.: Lawyer. 2007.

When concluding contracts outside the premises, non-fulfillment of information obligations may be due, in particular, to the absence of a signed application form. In this case, or if a copy of the application form has not been transferred to the consumer on another medium, the contract is invalid. Depending on the participants in electronic relations, a number of features of the regulation of these relations in EU law can be distinguished. The problem of the unequal position of the parties to some contracts has emerged. First of all, these are accession agreements with the participation of the consumer, the conclusion of which is actually carried out without preliminary negotiations. In this regard, national legislations introduce norms regarding unfair terms of the contract⁶.

It should be noted that the Central Asian countries have sufficient potential for the development of e-commerce. Mutual relations have already been established in the region to further develop relations between the countries. Also, the openness of the region to the whole world speaks about the great opportunities and advantages of the region. There are also a number of limitations and disadvantages of legal regulation of the field of e-commerce related to cybersecurity, low public confidence in electronic commerce, as well as certain economic problems.

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⁶ The Italian Civil Code of 1942